

Deliverable

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Abstract:

This document is meant to be an essay to report the latest progress made in ImAc project in accessibility service tools development.

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Statement of originality:

This document contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable acts as a report for all the progress made in this work package (WP4) and the new developments up to now. Also, a result for researches done is presented.

The main objective is to present all of the result in a concrete manner in order to make it easy for the reader to follow up the ImAc WP4 progress.

Chapter 1, explains the objectives of the work package and explains how this result will help and nourish other work packages and also from what work packages has received help. The relationships are clearly defined using a pert chart.

Chapter 2, explores and presents the progress made during first iteration of Subtitle production tools. Each tool developed by different partners (ANGLA, IRT and USAL) is specified to a separate sub-chapter with identical structure: First a general description is presented followed by respectively objectives, results and future work.

Chapter 3, explores Audio Description accessibility aspect and its progress during ImAc first iteration. The structure is similar to chapter 2 but this time the emphasis is put on the AD tools.

Chapter 4, shades light on Sign Language contents with the same structure used in chapter 2 and 3. in the first iteration this feature has been put aside due to technical reasons explained briefly in 4.1.

The deliverable is finished with a list of references.

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LIST OF ACRONYM

Acronym	Description
ACM	Accessibility Content Manager
ED	Editor interface
CM	Content Manager interface
SM	System Manager interface
AD	Audio Description
AST	Audio Subtitles
ST	Subtitling
SL	Sign Language
HUR	Home User Requirements
PUR	Professional User Requirements
WP	Work Package
ADM	Audio Definition Model
FOA	First Order Ambisonic
HOA	Higher Order Ambisonic
OBA	Object-based Audio

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. PURPOSE OF THIS DOCUMENT

As decided in first ImAc work packages, the Production tools should be able to handle three main accessibility content (ST, AD, SL). This objective has been achieved in the WP4 and all the tools have been explained individually in D4.1. D4.2 and D4.3. In WP4 and specifically during the first iteration, the technological basis for the content production of accessibility content in ImAc is developed. This comprises a comprehensive research on the accessibility content formats, investigations of existing tools and libraries, extending existing tools and the development of new production tools, handling existing and new file formats and convert between them and rendering accessibility content.

This document elaborates and aggregates all the results and progress made in WP4 in a single document D4.5.

1.2. SCOPE OF THIS DOCUMENT

This deliverable is meant to be a comprehensive report of the progress made in the first iteration of the ImAc in all of the WP tasks. Each task is specified to a chapter and each chapter is divided into different sub-chapters specified to different tools.

1.3. STATUS OF THIS DOCUMENT

This is an iterative document that depicts the progress made during the first development phase. The document will be updated after the second development phase in M24.

1.4. RELATION WITH OTHER ImAc WORKS

Illustration 1 shows the relation between this deliverable with other ImAc activities. As seen, we extract specifications and architecture design from D2.3 and D3.1 respectively. These help us in WP4 which focuses on accessibility services tools. In T4.1, T4.2 and T4.3 ImAc works on different aspects of the production tools investigation, development and enhancement. WP4 tools feed into T5.2 (content production for pilots). Findings that were made during the development also feed into standardisation activities (T6.2). All of the results and progresses are gathered and presented as deliverable D4.5.

Illustration 1: Pert diagram showing relation between deliverables

2. SUBTITLING PROGRESS

As explained in 1.1. first task of WP4 (T4.1) focuses on subtitling. In the first iteration of ImAc, the objective of T4.1 is defined to be development of technological basis for subtitling and also investigation of subtitles accessibility content formats and conversion tools with following goals:

- Provide production tools, suitable for producing and reviewing 360°/VR subtitles (see chapter 2.2)
- Investigate tools for converting existing subtitle formats into 360°/VR subtitle and check file quality (see chapter 2.3)
- Investigating open source tools usage on subtitle production for 360°/VR (see chapter 2.4)
- Mapping the specifications from T2.3 to a suitable TTML-based subtitle format.
- Investigate various rendering strategies for subtitles in VR (see chapter 2.3 and 2.4)

In this chapter, in each section we describe the results obtained and the future work for each subtitle production tool. Additionally, chapter 2.1 provides an overview of the relationship between the tools involved in T4.1.

2.1. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DIFFERENT SUBTITLE TOOLS

This chapter describes the relationship between the different ImAc development activities regarding subtitling. In ImAc the major development activities are divided into two major iteration phases, with user pilots at the end of each phase.

Various tools are being developed in ImAc to realize or prepare realization of the ImAc subtitle services. Since all web-based tools are partly based on the same JavaScript libraries, software components can easily be shared between partners and can be reused in other ImAc tools.

The following table provides an overview of the relationship between these tools. The table highlights where components or developed concepts are being reused. It does not reflect the integration of these tools in the overall ImAc platform.

Tool	Notes / relation to other ImAc tools	Responsible partner
ImAc player (WP3)	<p>From WP3: The end user ImAc player (web-tool / browser based)</p> <p>Relation to other ImAc tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Provides:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ ImAc subtitle rendering component/concept • <u>Uses:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Subtitle rendering component/concept from <i>IMSC_VR Authoring Tool</i> <p>(Note: Development of ImAc subtitle rendering component and concept is partially done in <i>ImAc player</i> and partially in <i>IMSC_VR Authoring Tool</i>)</p> <p>Activities during:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>1st iteration phase:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Implementation of rendering concept (initial version) • <u>2nd iteration phase:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Integrate improvements of rendering concept developed in <i>IMSC_VR Authoring Tool</i> 	I2CAT
Web ST Editor	<p>Web editor for evaluating a subtitling production UI with features for 360° subtitles (web-tool / browser based)</p> <p>Relation to other ImAc tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Provides:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Results of user tests for subtitling production UI. • <u>Uses:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ ImAc subtitle rendering component/concept (from <i>ImAc player, IMSC_VR Authoring Tool</i>) for preview. <p>Activities during:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>1st iteration phase:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Implementation of experimental subtitling production tool. ◦ Run and evaluate professional user tests • <u>2nd iteration phase:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Add subtitle rendering component for HMD preview. ◦ Add new functionalities after the professional evaluation for a professional web production tool. 	ANGLA
Fingertext	Professional subtitle editor (standalone desktop software)	ANGLA

Editor	<p>Relation to other ImAc tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Provides:</u> N/A • <u>Uses:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Results of user tests for subtitling production UI (from Web ST Editor). ○ ImAc subtitle rendering component/concept (from <i>ImAc player</i>, <i>IMSC_VR Authoring Tool</i>) for preview. Results of user tests for authoring UI (from <i>Web ST Editor</i>) <p>Activities during:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>1st iteration phase:</u> N/A • <u>2nd iteration phase:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Implement the subtitling production UI for 360° media and authoring functionalities on the existing professional Fingertext editor 	
IMSC_VR Authoring Tool	<p>Reference implementation for a standardized IMSC-based data model for subtitles in 360° and VR (web-tool / browser based)</p> <p>Relation to other ImAc tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Provides:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ ImAc subtitle rendering component/concept • <u>Uses:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Results of user tests for subtitling production UI (from Web ST Editor) ◆ ImAc subtitle rendering component/concept from <i>ImAc player</i> <p>(Note: Development of ImAc subtitle rendering component and concept is partially done in <i>ImAc player</i> and partially in <i>IMSC_VR Authoring Tool</i>)</p> <p>Activities during:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>1st iteration phase:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Implementation of test environment for different rendering strategies ◆ Implementation of rendering concept (initial version) • <u>2nd iteration phase:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Improve ImAc rendering concept ◆ Run additional user tests to evaluate rendering concept ◆ Integrate subtitling production functionalities (based on results from <i>Web ST Editor</i>) 	IRT
Subtitle Conversion Framework (SCF)	<p>Tool for converting between different subtitle formats</p> <p>Relation to other tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Provides:</u> N/A • <u>Uses:</u> N/A <p>(Only relation: The SCF needs to process the subtitle format that is defined in ImAc)</p>	IRT

	<p>Activities during:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>1st iteration phase:</u> N/A • <u>2nd iteration phase:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Adapt SCF to support ImAc subtitle format 	
<p>Responsive Subtitle Prototype</p>	<p>Prototype implementation of responsive subtitle approach for a 360 video, including basic editing and responsive subtitle playback, from within the immersive environment</p>	<p>USAL</p>
	<p>Relation to other tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Provides:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ ImAc responsive subtitle concept • <u>Uses:</u> N/A 	
	<p>Activities during:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>1st iteration phase:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Implementation of a proof of concept in order to evaluate and demonstrate the feasibility of responsive subtitles for 360 video ◆ Implemented a basic video editor to evaluate the feasibility of edition and positioning subtitles from within an immersive environment • <u>2nd iteration phase:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Extend demo to support ImAc subtitle format, and ensure that the ImAc subtitle format is suitable for responsive subtitles. ◆ A user evaluation of the tools 	

Table 1: Overview of the relationship between different subtitle production tools

2.2. EDITOR INTERFACE AND WEB ST EDITOR

For this first iteration the Editor interface (see illustration 2) and a Web ST Editor (see illustration 3) have been developed.

Illustration 2: Editor interface

Illustration 3: Web ST Editor

2.2.1. General description

The Editor interface is a place in which the professional users can see and navigate the tasks that have been assigned to them previously from the Content Manager interface. These tasks can be either a ST, AD or SL. In this subsection we deal with ST tasks which are performed by the integrated Web ST Editor. For the second iteration the Editor interface will also integrate with an external Windows ST Editor that will be developed during the second iteration from existing professional one.

The Web ST Editor is the tool that allows the professional user to edit the ST task assigned to them. In a way we can say it's the production tool to create/edit subtitles.

In the first iteration of ImAc a Web ST Editor has been developed. This editor lets the user create/edit subtitles for media which low quality video has been uploaded to an asset of the Content Manager. The editor mainly relies on existing concepts available for subtitle services, however new features have been added to it according to the specifications derived from

previous work packages. In 2.2.2 the main objectives for this editor is going to be presented, while in 2.2.3 the obtained result will be available. In 2.2.4 the pending objectives and work for second iteration will be presented.

2.2.2. Objectives

As stated before, ImAc is a user-centric project which has extracted its specifications from user scenarios and focus groups. According to these previous work packages, we have developed some objectives to look into at the moment of development. It is important to note that this document pays special attention to PUR as the result of this work package mainly interacts with professional users, home users may not have any relation with the result of it. We divide these specifications into two sub-categories:

1. General goals elaborated in D2.3 document.
2. Specific requirements elaborated in D2.2 with their specifications.

The work done is based on these two sub-categories.

1. General goals elaborated in D2.3 ^[1]:

- **Subtitle characteristics:** the TV broadcast subtitle services are still based on the teletext limitations as well as on viewer behaviour, including their reading speed. That implies that the number of characters is limited to about 37 characters per line and it is suggested to use not more than 2 lines for a subtitle.
- **Colours for distinguishing different characters:** it is considered that at minimum 4 colours are used for different characters. Also colour palettes for colour-blinded people should be determined.
- **Subtitle position:** it is necessary to define positions for the text. The subtitles were positioned centered, bottom left, bottom right, top left and top right to show the limits of the comfortable field of view. The default presentation of RBB's HbbTV subtitles in a medium size (40px according to HD resolution of 720px height) with an adapted black background (80% opacity), a maximum of two lines and 37 characters per line was used as a starting point. It was obvious that the font size needs to be adapted according to the comfortable field of view to avoid additional line breaks.
- **Subtitle presentation:** the subtitles will be always presented on the same device on which the omnidirectional video is being presented. The use of additional screens for exclusively presenting subtitles is not an option desired by end-users. In addition, subtitles will be always visible in the basic presentation mode (centered in the defined field of view), regardless of whether the related scenes/objects in the 360° area are visible or not.
- **Subtitle personalization options:** in case that multiple subtitle tracks are available, users will be able to select between them (HUR.02.25.00). This will include multiple languages, and normal vs. easy-to-read subtitles. Different font sizes (e.g. small, medium and large) for the presentation of subtitles will be available (HUR.02.29.00). In addition, the users will be able to select between different backgrounds: 1) semi-transparent box (80% opacity); 2) outline (2px for each font size); and 3) adding the subtitles below a scaled down video area (HUR.02.30.0). Regarding their position, subtitles are typically visible in the user's field of view in the middle slightly below eye line, two-lined. The ImAc player will follow this

approach (HUR.02.27.0), but it will allow dynamically setting different positions, as also required by users during the conducted focus groups. The most appropriate vertical position for subtitles depends on the user device (i.e. viewing environment) and/or on the user. Therefore, personalization options will be provided and some tests will be conducted in that sense in order to find out the most comfortable consumption experience. Appropriate and intuitive controls to set the mentioned presentation functionalities and modes will be provided in the player.

- **Presentation of visual notifications for sounds:** the player will also provide visual notifications, as icons, when relevant sound related events are being presented, enabling their interpretation by the hearing-impaired users.

2. Specific PURs elaborated in D2.2^[2] with their specifications:

Req. Nr.	Title	Description
PUR.01.01.0	Watch low-res preview content	The user must be able to watch the preview content in low quality as flat folded or flat unfolded view.
PUR.01.02.0	Watch high-res preview content	The user must be able to watch the preview content in high quality as HMD view.
PUR.01.03.0	Navigate preview content by angle	The user must be able to watch content and to navigate it with the help of keyboard shortcuts, scroll wheel and input fields by angle.
PUR.01.04.0	Navigate preview content by frame	The user must be able to watch content and to navigate it with the help of keyboard shortcuts, scroll wheel and input fields by frame number.
PUR.01.05.0	Navigate preview content by time	The user must be able to watch content and to navigate it with the help of keyboard shortcuts, scroll wheel and input fields by time code.
PUR.01.06.0	Navigate preview content by audio	The user must be able to hear 360° audio together with graphical elements that inform about the orientation of the current view.
PUR.01.07.0	File operations	The user must be able to perform file operations such as import or export files (video and ImAc files).
PUR.01.08.0	Add subtitle text	The user must be able to produce subtitle texts by (1) inserting text with keyboard, (2) symbols from a library and adding it all to the video with the following ordered steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Defining vertical and horizontal position and font size 2. Defining time-code and duration 3. Defining font colour 4. Defining viewing angle

PUR.03.01.0	Accessing content for ImAc content	The user should use a GUI for accessing omnidirectional (video) and ImAc content files (ST, SL video, AD) for selecting and uploading/downloading files.
PUR.03.02.0	Checking content for ImAc enrichment	The user should be able to check ImAc media regarding: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. File name 2. File size 3. Content type 4. Integrity 5. Assignment
PUR.03.03.0	Assigning content for ImAc enrichment	The user should be able to assign ImAc files to omnidirectional media files.

Table 2: Professional User Requirements in ST production tool

What mainly done in WP4 was to take a deep look at I and II sections above and start working on the Editor interface and the Web ST Editor. Section 2.2.3. explains the result obtained.

2.2.3. Results

In the previous chapter, the objectives of subtitles presentation and edition were presented. In this section we explain how many of this objectives and to what extent have been developed to this date. As mentioned in 1.3, this document is updated gradually as the project moves forward.

In this chapter only a general description will be presented, for more detailed information and for test purposes, the user manual of the Web ST Editor and the access to its interface can be found in the D4.1 deliverable ^[3]. Since D4.1 includes installation guide, comprehensive user manual with images, user centric scenarios which help the reader understand the tool better, here we skip elaborating in detail and we only present the results along with some important points.

This section will present the result according to PURs provided in previous chapter:

PUR.01.08.0	Add subtitle text
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<p>Result</p>	<p>According to the PURs which are closely related to subtitle creation/edition, the above image has been developed. Using the available tools, the user can edit subtitles and then navigate through them for possible corrections. A possible work flow scenario is as follows and it is divided into two parts: a) edition 2) verification. Edition (“edit” mode) is the part of the work where the subtitler starts to enter the texts and edit them and also chooses proper settings and time constants for each of them, while verification (“free preview” or “forced preview” modes) is when the subtitler wants to check the result. For more information on how every mode of preview works, the reader should study D4.1 carefully. The numbers are compatible with the above image numbering:</p> <p>Edition (“edit” mode):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Entering the text of the subtitle in the text area using the keyboard. 2. The shape and format of the subtitle is adjusted. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Defining vertical and horizontal position by selecting a region. Region settings can be edited by right clicking over the corresponding button. ○ Defining font size and colour by selecting one character. Character settings can be edited by right clicking over the corresponding character button. A keyboard shortcut can be used as well. 3. The user can navigate through subtitles using different buttons in “Move” section. 4. In “Actions”, the user can add or remove subtitles, assign in and out Time Constants and set current angle. 5. Finally in the section “Find/Replace” the user, if necessary, can find and replace words of the texts. 6. The full text is available on the right side of the page. <p>Verification (“Free preview” and “Forced preview” modes):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. At the end, the user can go to section “Mode”, and change the mode from “Edit” to “Forced preview” or “Free preview” in order to verify the result of their work. <p>All of the above mentioned actions can be done via mouse buttons or keyboard shortcuts.</p>
<p>Pending</p>	<p>PUR.01.06.0</p>

Table 3: Subtitle creation/edition in Web ST Editor

PUR.01.01.0	Watch low-res preview content
PUR.01.02.0	Watch high-res preview content
PUR.01.03.0	Navigate preview content by angle
PUR.01.04.0	Navigate preview content by frame
PUR.01.05.0	Navigate preview content by time
PUR.01.06.0	Navigate preview content by audio

Result

Similar to table 3, we have separated the PURs related to video navigation and divided them into two sub-categories of edition and verification modes. The numbers are compatible with the numbering in the above image.

Edition (“edit” mode):

This mode is used during the subtitle edition process. The user can navigate through the Low Quality video during the edition of one subtitle to preview the video and also locate the right positions.

1. The buttons in the “video controls” section are used to navigate through the video, also by frame and time.
2. The buttons in the second row of the “move” section are used to change the field of view of the video preview to locate the speaker in the 360° video.

Verification (“Free preview” and “Forced preview” modes):

3. At the moment of verification there are two options for the user:
 - Free preview: this mode is used for the verification of the subtitling. Subtitles are bound to the video time code, but angle is not. It means that navigating through the video using the “video control” buttons you can also move angle (it is not fixed to the speaker), so it makes the verification process more real as if playing back the video with subtitles using

	<p>HMD.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forced preview: this mode is used for the verification of the subtitling. This verification mode makes it easier for the subtitler as the video will change angle when needed during the playback of the video. Subtitles and angle are bound with the video. It means that navigating through the video using the “video control” buttons, the angle of the field of view will change automatically to the speaker location to ease the verification process. <p>In this version it is only possible to verify the result in LQ. In the future these modes will be used to see the result in HQ using HMD.</p>
Pending	<p>High resolution preview (PUR.01.02.0) will be implemented using HMD. Navigate preview content by audio</p> <p>(PUR.01.06.0) is still not implemented in this iteration</p>

Table 4: Video navigation PURs

PUR.03.02.0	Checking content for ImAc enrichment
PUR.01.07.0	File operations
PUR.03.01.0	Accessing content for ImAc content
PUR.03.03.0	Assigning content for ImAc enrichment

Result	The PURs mentioned in these tables have been developed successfully in the first iteration but in a different interface (CM).
Pending	The objective for the second iteration is to integrate the Editor interface with a professional Windows ST Editor, so some of this requirements will also be possible from the editor (PUR.01.07.0).

Table 5: Content Manager interface PURs related to subtitling

2.2.4. Future work and second iteration

This section wants to take a look at the intended future work to be done in the development of ImAc ST Production Tools.

- As seen in 2.2.3. some of the PURs are still remaining up to this date. Table 6 shows the PURs pending to be done.

Req. Nr.	Title	Description
PUR.01.02.0	Watch high-res preview content	The user must be able to watch the preview content in high quality as HMD view.
PUR.01.06.0	Navigate preview content by audio	The user must be able to hear 360° audio together with graphical elements that inform about the orientation of the current view.

Table 6: Remaining PURs in ST Production Tool (first iteration)

- After the results of the pre-pilots and the pilots some improvement will be implemented in the web based editors and ACM.
- During the second iteration the Windows ST Editor will be developed from an existing professional one and integrated with the Editor interface.

2.3. SUBTITLE CONVERSION FRAMEWORK

2.3.1. General description

The Subtitling Conversion Framework (SCF) is a set of modules for converting XML-based subtitle formats. The tool includes conversion between the current standard subtitle format in Broadcast (EBU STL) and EBU-TT, which is very closely related with IMSC, the TTML-based subtitle format that is used as a basis in ImAc.

SCF is published under the Apache 2.0 license on github.com (see Table 7).

Description	Link
SCF (documentation & source code)	https://github.com/Irt-Open-Source/scf https://github.com/Irt-Open-Source/scf
TTML standard	https://www.w3.org/TR/ttml2/
EBU-TT standard family	https://tech.ebu.ch/subtitling https://tech.ebu.ch/subtitling
IMSC standard	https://www.w3.org/TR/ttml-imsc1.0.1/

Table 7: List of links relevant to SCF

2.3.2. Objectives

Main target of the SCF is to build up a flexible and extensible transformation pipeline to convert EBU STL formats and EBU-TT subtitle formats.

In ImAc, the SCF is used to allow a better integration of ImAc subtitle production into existing subtitle workflows. Especially that means, that the subtitle format used in ImAc shall be supported by the SCF, such that:

- Subtitles that were produced in EBU STL can be used as a basis in ImAc (module “STLXML2EBU-TT”),
- Subtitles that were produced in the ImAc subtitle format can be converted into EBU STL or EBU-TT (module “EBU-TT2STLXML” – ImAc extensions will be dropped or mapped in this process) and
- The helper modules in SCF can be used for ImAc subtitle files (for example the module “TT-edit-list”, that can apply an edit list to a subtitle file and automatically adjust all timecode values).

2.3.3. Results

During the first iteration of ImAc only two additional attributes have been added to IMSC: latitude and longitude values that describe a direction in 3D space.

Since these extensions are not critical for the conversion process, no ImAc related implementation work has been done for the SCF during the first iteration.

A short test has been conducted to check the compatibility of ImAc subtitle files with the SCF. The result of this test was positive.

2.3.4. Future work and second iteration

The second iteration may add further extensions to the ImAc subtitle format. An example could be to use a metric for length values that is not supported by (native) IMSC. That will likely lead to additional requirements for the conversion algorithms.

In the second iteration, these requirements will be collected and the SCF will be extended accordingly if needed, such that it supports the subtitle format defined in ImAc.

2.4. EXPERIMENTAL IMSC_VR AUTHORING TOOL

2.4.1. General description

The IMSC_VR Authoring Tool is an experimental software component, that accompanies the work on defining an IMSC-based subtitle format. As such, it includes features to test different subtitle presentation modes. Additionally, it implements the ImAc subtitle format for 360°/VR media.

2.4.2. Objectives

The objectives of this tool are:

- Providing an experimental 360° subtitle rendering implementation for demonstrating and testing the rendering concept for subtitles in 360° and VR.

- Providing an open source reference implementation for a standardized IMSC-based data model for subtitles in 360° and VR.

2.4.3. Results

In the first iteration of ImAc, subtitle presentation options have been implemented as described in D4.1. Early feedback from pre-pilot user tests were considered during this process.

Additionally, the work on this topic revealed several issues regarding the definition of a 360°/VR subtitle format.

During the initial phase of ImAc, the requirement for a subtitle format extension regarding positioning was determined. The most basic requirement is to connect a subtitle with a position in the VR/360° environment.

2.4.4. Future work and second iteration

At the beginning of second ImAc iteration the subtitle presentation will be improved and validated in small scale user tests. For this purpose, the IMSC_VR Authoring Tool will be extended by an additional presentation mode. The goal is to develop a presentation mode that provides a more immersive experience for users, especially when Head Mounted Displays (HMD) are used.

As presented by Sylvia Rothe at TVX2018^[4], viewers find it more comfortable when subtitles are positioned next to the speaking person rather than at a static position in the field of view. As a drawback, the viewer might miss subtitles when looking around the scene. This presentation mode is not suitable for any content but is believed to enhance the user experience.

ImAc aims to adapt this presentation mode and investigate if the mode can be enhanced in such a way that it is less likely to miss subtitle information. This presentation mode is intended to be available as an optional mode, which a user may select for subtitle presentation.

In parallel, authoring features will be implemented such that all ImAc extensions for VR purposes can be edited and tested. The tool will be provided as an open source implementation for an IMSC-based, VR compatible and standard compliant subtitle format.

During the first iteration phase, ImAc already added IMSC extensions for connecting a subtitle with a position in the VR/360° environment. For using IMSC in VR, two further issues were identified and are being discussed:

1. Provide a reference to the underlying video.
2. Investigate the implications of different metrics in 3D space.

A comprehensive proposal for a VR/360° subtitle format, will be delivered in D4.4.

2.5. RESPONSIVE SUBTITLING

2.5.1. General description

Our responsive approach enables the subtitles to be formatted in the device to fit the display

capabilities (based on previous work ^[5]). It also provides the flexibility to respond to changes made by the user to personalize the subtitles to fit their own requirements. This is achieved by sending 'atomized' subtitles with timing for each word and formatting the subtitle blocks in the client device. This means that the block formatting can take account of the device characteristics and user preferences to provide a tailored and completely custom user experience.

2.5.2. Objectives

The main objective is to demonstrate how responsive subtitles can work with a 360° Head Mounted Display and provide feedback for the ImAc development. For that it is necessary to take into account:

- Subtitle automisation: we need to be able to break the lines down into individual atoms as our re-blocking mechanism requires per word timings. Previous work has shown this can be done phonetically in order to align each word with the audio signal^[7]. However this can be done with reasonable success by interpolating a time for each word based on its position in the block and the start and end time of the block. In the case of live subtitles, where the subtitler has updated the subtitles as each word is spoken, this can be done more intelligently. Live subtitle files usually contain both individual words, which are blocked only when the subtitler gets to the end of a line. To make use of these subtitles our approach is to load only the individual words, and disregard the repeated blocks.

Illustration 4: The atomised subtitle are re-blocked into groups with maximum character length of (a) 22 or (b) 62

Both methods provide a good list of words with individual timings, as shown in illustration 4.

- Best fit: It is in the nature of responsive subtitles that the user is given control to change the font size and style that they wish to be used for displaying the subtitles as

well as changing the display size. It is therefore up to the renderer to work out how many characters can be fit into each line.

- Re-blocking: The subtitles are re-blocked by adhering to the number of characters that can fit into the display division at the chosen font size.

2.5.3. Results

Our example implementation provides an enhanced prototype video player, using Unity to display the correct subtitle in time with the video and dynamically re-block the subtitles as a response to user interaction. The video player consists of two components. The first is contains an 'Skybox' Material which is used to render the equirectangular video and a plane provides a container for the current subtitle. Other basic functionality such as the ability to reposition the subtitle container above are also implemented.

Atomised subtitle data is stored as individual words, mapped to their display timings and speaker identification, providing a base for generating new blocked subtitles as required. If an event occurs that required the subtitles to be re-blocked (such as the subtitle container being resized, or the user changing the font size) they are recalculated and stored as temporary strings containing the text and style information, along with start time for the each block. In our prototype we assume that it is safe to always have a subtitle displayed and therefore don't currently store the end time, assuming that it is safe to display the subtitle until it is replaced.

Should a break be required an empty subtitle can be inserted. Functions are provided for loading subtitles from either our enhanced subtitle files, which contain per-word timing, or from conventional STL or TTML files which are atomized as they are loaded.

An event listener periodically checks the position of the video against the start times of the blocked subtitles. If the video position has passed the boundary into a new subtitle then the subtitle division is updated appropriately.

2.5.4. Future work and second iteration

During the second iteration a full user study will be completed to test our prototype. The results from this user test will provide answers and ideas that will feedback into the full ImAc player. Subtitle formats will also be standardized with the ImAc platform to ensure full compatibility.

3. ENHANCED AUDIO SERVICES PROGRESS

As explained in 1.1. second task of WP4 (T4.2) focuses on audio services. In the first iteration of ImAc, the objective of T4.2 is defined to be development of technological basis for audio services and also investigation of AD accessibility content formats and conversion tools with following goals:

- Evolution of current audio services tools (see chapter 3.2)
- Investigate technical solutions and suitable formats for preparing and delivering 3D audio with AD to target devices and platforms, following user requirements from T2.2.
- Provide production and editing tools following the results from the preceding bullet point.

In this section, the progress in the tools for the audio services is presented, result and the intended future work, but before there is a section (chapter 3.1) to observe the relationship between the tools involved in this chapter.

3.1. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DIFFERENT AUDIO TOOLS

Unlike the subtitle developments, the audio description tools do not share any software components and are developed separate from each other. The ImAc workflow as well as the specified interfaces are described in D3.1.

3.2. WEB AD EDITOR

For this first iteration the Editor interface (see illustration 2) and a Web AD Editor (see illustration 5) have been developed.

The Editor interface is a place in which the professional users can see and navigate the tasks that have been assigned to them previously from the Content Manager interface. These tasks can be either a ST, AD or SL. In this subsection we deal with AD tasks which are performed by the integrated Web AD Editor. For the second iteration the Editor interface will also integrate with an external Windows AD Editor that will be developed during the second iteration from existing professional one.

Illustration 5: Web AD Editor environment

3.2.1. General description

What mainly done here is evolving the current audio editor tools to add support for 360° video and to edit enhanced metadata elements. As seen before the user requirements are extracted from D2.2 and the specifications are from D2.3. it is very important for this tool to maintain its compatibility to the current audio description tools. In 3.2.2. we will take a look at the objectives that were extracted from D2.2 and D2.3 and then in 3.2.3. we see how we have developed the result based on 3.2.2. Finally in 3.2.4. we explain the work to be done in this area.

3.2.2. Objectives

Similar to 2.2.2. we first present the specifications needed for the tool and then the Professional User Requirements are presented as objectives of this development as two sub-categories:

1. General goals elaborated in D2.3 document.
 2. Specific requirements elaborated in D2.2 with their specifications.
- 1. General goals elaborated in D2.3 (only related to professional users):**
- **Presentation of immersive/spatial audio in general:** the principal objective of this task is that the listener feels like he/she is located within the presented (audio) scene and that listener can locate sound sources in different directions. According to the past projects and also the focus groups test results a spatially stable audio scene is desired in ImAc.
 - **Locations of AD speaker in the audio scene:** ImAc will support immersive audio that allows for additional options regarding the location of the AD speaker. ImAc will evaluate what AD speaker location will be most comfortable to the user. Three different options will be tested:
 1. AD centered in the scene (Voice of God).

2. AD anchored in the scene (Friend on Sofa).
3. AD anchored on the event/object being described (AD on action).

2. Specific PURs elaborated in D2.2 with their specifications:

Req. Nr.	Title	Description
PUR.01.01.0	Watch low-res preview content	The user must be able to watch the preview content in low quality as flat folded or flat unfolded view.
PUR.01.02.0	Watch hi-res preview content	The user must be able to watch the preview content in high quality as HMD view.
PUR.01.03.0	Navigate preview content by angle	The user must be able to watch content and to navigate it with the help of keyboard shortcuts, scroll wheel and input fields by angle.
PUR.01.04.0	Navigate preview content by frame	The user must be able to watch content and to navigate it with the help of keyboard shortcuts, scroll wheel and input fields by frame number.
PUR.01.05.0	Navigate preview content by time	The user must be able to watch content and to navigate it with the help of keyboard shortcuts, scroll wheel and input fields by time code.
PUR.01.07.0	File operations	The user must be able to perform file operations such as import or export files (video and ImAc files).
PUR.01.10.0	Create AD preview content	The user must be able to feed a written AD script and start a text-to-speech process.
PUR.01.11.0	Add AD preview audio to video	The user must be able to add a text-to-speech AD result to a video as additional audio asset.
PUR.01.12.0	Preview video and AD audio	The user must be able to preview the video together with the added speech-to-text AD asset.
PUR.01.13.0	Add audio description	The user should be able to add a number of simultaneous audio descriptions to different sections of the visual scene.
PUR.03.01.0	Accessing content for ImAc enrichment	The user should use a GUI for accessing omnidirectional (video) and ImAc content files (ST, SL video, AD) for selecting and uploading/downloading files.

Table 8: Professional User Requirements in AD Production tool

3.2.3. Results

Next subject to be observed is the result obtained from 3.2.2. the PURs and the goals helped ImAc WP4 to develop the current Web AD Editor. The following data and tables show how many of these PURs have been achieved and to what extent.

In this chapter only a general description will be presented, for more detailed information and for test purposes, the user manual of the Web AD Editor and the access to its interface can be found in the D4.2 deliverable ^[8]. D4.2 contains clear user manual, a manual on how to install the tool and scenarios and images on how a user can work with Web AD Editor.

In 3.2.3. we have divided PURs to four different categories based on their concept: 1. Navigation 2. Edition 3. Verification 4. Content management.

The tables below explain the results obtained in respect to the above mentioned categories:

PUR.01.01.0	Watch low-res preview content
PUR.01.02.0	Watch high-res preview content
PUR.01.03.0	Navigate preview content by angle
PUR.01.04.0	Navigate preview content by frame
PUR.01.05.0	Navigate preview content by time

Results

Below we explain how the above PURs have been achieved. The numbers are compatible with the image numbering above:

1. The user can navigate through the video using classic video buttons in LQ mode. Using keyboard shortcuts is possible too in order to work easier and faster. This way they can navigate the video by frame and time-code
2. The user can see section “Actions”, and find the part in which they can choose a latitude and longitude and navigate the video by angle.

In the first iteration of ImAc, only navigation in LQ has been possible.

Pending

PUR.01.02.0

Table 9: Video navigation

PUR.01.10.0	Create AD preview content
PUR.01.11.0	Add AD preview audio to video
PUR.01.13.0	Add audio description

Result

Below we explain how the above PURs have been achieved. The numbers are compatible with the image numbering above:

However, first we would like to elaborate why we have different modes for edition and verification. As seen in the image in the “Mode” section, there are 3 different modes. In this table we are elaboration a situation in which we are editing, hence we are in the “edit” mode. This mode is used during the AD edition process. The user can move freely via the AD segments and edit them as they wish.

1. First step is to create the script that the user will record, as if it was a subtitling, but describing the different scenes of the video. In each segment, the user will have to type the text, and set the TC IN (Shift+Page Down) and TC OUT (Shift+Page Up), while playing/pausing the video (Alt+F2), or frame by frame as well (Alt+left/right).
2. For every segment, it is possible to add a desired angle and navigate through these segments for edition purposes.
3. Once script is created, the user will record the first audio segment using the options on the right bottom side, clicking on the “Record” button. A countdown will appear, so that the user can prepare for the segment recording. Once finished, the user will click on the “Stop” button to stop the recording procedure. Then the user can check the current segment audio recording by clicking either on “Short test” or on the “Long test” buttons. The user can also record the segment again if needed. Finally, an attenuation (in the “attenuation” section) can be added if the video volume is to high to hear the audio description segment properly, by selecting the desired attenuation from the Recording controls section.
4. The scripts of all of the segments are seen on the right.

As seen, all of the actions above are done in LQ resolution. This is strictly possible when we are in “edit” mode. The shortcuts are made available.

Table 10: AD Content Edition

The screenshot displays the Web AD Editor interface. On the left, the 'Asset details' panel shows information for 'Title: Life On Mars 1', 'Programme ID: 17267803', and 'Language: Catalan'. Below this are 'Video controls' and 'Segment controls'. The central video preview window shows three people in a room, with a subtitle 'Es veuen les lletres d'inici' overlaid. To the right, the 'Asset actions' panel includes a 'Segment list' with 8 entries, each with start and end times and a description. At the bottom right, the 'Recording controls' panel offers options for 'Short test' and 'Long test', along with audio level and fading settings.

Results

At the moment of verification there are two options for the user:

- Free preview: this mode is used for the verification of the AD segments. Segments are bound to the video time code, but angle is not. It means that navigating through the video using the “video control” buttons you can also move angle (it is not fixed to the speaker), so it makes the verification process more real as if playing back the video with AD using HMD.
- Forced preview: this mode is used for the verification of the AD segments. This verification mode makes it easier for the user as the video will change angle when needed during the playback of the video. AD segments and angle are bound with the video. It means that navigating through the video using the “video control” buttons, the angle of the field of view will change automatically to the speaker location to ease the verification process.

In this version it is only possible to verify the result in LQ. In the future these modes will be used to see the result in HQ using HMD.

Table 11: AD content verification

PUR.01.07.0	File operations
PUR.03.01.0	Accessing content for ImAc enrichment
Result	In the first iteration these features have been implemented in CM interface.
Pending	The objective for the second iteration is to integrate the Editor interface with a professional Windows AD Editor, so some of this requirements will also be possible from the editor (PUR.01.07.0).

Table 12: Content Manager interface PURs related to audio description

3.2.4. Future work and second iteration

This section wants to take a look at the intended future work to be done in the development of ImAc AD Production Tools.

- As seen in 3.2.3. some of the PURs are still remaining up to this date. Table 14 shows the PURs pending to be done.

Req. Nr.	Title	Description
PUR.01.02.0	Watch high-res preview content	The user must be able to watch the preview content in high quality as HMD view.

Table 13: Remaining PURs in AD Production Tool (first iteration)

- After the results of the pre-pilots and the pilots some improvement will be implemented in the web based editors and ACM.
- During the second iteration the Windows based editors for accessibility content will be developed and integrated with the Editor interface.

3.3. CLOUD RENDERER

3.3.1. General description

The Cloud Renderer is a software settled in a serverless architecture and works as “Software as a Service” (SaaS) in the cloud. It is a service to attach interactive audio content to an audio scene or a channel-based audio (OBA) production. In the domain of ImAc, interactive audio content means Audio Description segments, which can be placed in a 3D sphere and which can be leveled interactively by the customer. The pre-processed audio variants can be rendered into a number of common audio formats (like wav or AAC). The software pre-renders different versions of the immersive content and uploads the results to a defined web space.

In the ImAc workflow, the Cloud Renderer downloads all the files it needs (Audio Description segments and the configuration file, and/or an ADM file) from a defined URL, merges the Audio Description into the object-based audio scene, renders different variants of the AD and the audio scene and uploads the results to the specified web destination.

3.3.2. Objectives

The main objectives of this tool are:

- Add support for the ADM format: The rendering algorithm and the API must be made capable for processing the ADM standard (as of ITU-R BS.2076, Audio Definition Model^[9]). ADM is an open and standardized production format for OBA. As such, it allows an interoperable exchange of these production files between different systems.
- Enhance processor to support additional AD parameters: For the ImAc use cases, two OBA parameters were defined to be variable. The position of an AD sequence within the 3D audio space is adjustable – the user may select from different options later. Three different positions are suggested in ImAc – Voice of God, Friend on sofa and “dynamic” position. The specification of different gain levels is the second parameter, which has to be addressed. Hereby, the AD editor may define different volume levels for AD (e.g. high, medium, low) within a range between 0 and 1. The renderer must be enhanced to process these parameters as a list of options (instead of a static value).
- Add ImAc API: Adapt IRT cloud software to meet the requirements of the API and the web API gateway as defined in ImAc.

3.3.3. Results

In the first iteration of ImAc, two additional parameters for AD tracks were defined and implemented in a (proprietary) ImAc-format. This format describes AD tracks as OBA assets/objects in order to either add them to an OBA scene (in case the main audio production was done object-based) or to mix them with a channel-based production (stereo, FOA, ...). Support for mixing AD objects into channel-based production was added. The renderer is able to process the ImAc AD-files together with a channel-based main mix into the formats First Order Ambisonic (FOA), stereo and static binaural.

3.3.4. Future work and second iteration

The specified ImAc API as well as the notification callback API must be implemented to be natively addressable. Additionally, the ADM format must be integrated. A web front-end will be developed in order to allow a user-friendly manual control of rendering jobs.

3.4. OBJECT-BASED AUDIO EDITOR

3.4.1. General description

The object-based editor with graphical user interface was developed by IRT. It allows users to create and author object-based audio scenes, control the object positions but also other metadata, such as gain. It also controls the signal processing/rendering and can be synchronized to any DAW via MTC (Midi Time Code) and MMC (Midi Machine Control).

Object-based audio is the future standard for audio production in broadcast environments, therefore the development of this editor is important for ImAc to be state of the art.

Object-based audio provides a simple way to integrate barrier-free services and provide all kind of barrier-free content. Immersive sound can be provided easily to the users, the audio mix is custom-made for any sound-system and is therefore in a better quality and with more possibilities of usability. AD can be used more flexible and with a lot more possibilities than in standard formats. Separate gain adjustments for the AD and different kinds of AD mixes can be easily provided.

The Audio Definition Model (ADM), is a metadata model to describe all sorts of audio contents and formats. Besides traditional channel-based audio it also supports scene-based audio like Higher Order Ambisonic (HOA) and object-based audio. For audio description purposes, the ADM element *audioContent* is particularly interesting. It describes the content of one component of a program (e.g. dialog), and references one or more *audioObject* elements to tie the content to its format. To further describe the content it provides sub-elements to indicate whether it consists of *dialog*, *non-dialog* or a *mix* of both. For the dialog kind, it is additionally possible to explicitly state, that the content only contains *audio description* or dialog for the *visually impaired*. The mixed content kind can be moreover specified as content for the hearing impaired.

3.4.2. Objectives

The main objectives of this tool are:

- Integration of the ADM standard in the object-based audio editor.
- It is important for the ImAc project to implement the ADM standard in the object-based audio editor because this is the future format for audio production in broadcast environments. To be up to date and ready for all future developments AD should already be considered in developments with this standard.
- Integrate ImAc requirements for AD into ADM. That may result in a proposal for ADM extensions.

3.4.3. Results

In the first iteration of ImAc, the integration of ADM has started but is not complete yet. ADM supports a wide range of parameters which need to be supported by the audio processor in order to render a correct representation of the ADM scene. Additionally, the present implementation of the editor does not suit the requirements of the ADM yet. During iteration 1, the tool has been prepared for a standard compliant import and export of a basic ADM feature set.

3.4.4. Future work and second iteration

At the beginning of second ImAc iteration the integration process of ADM will continue. The feature set of the ADM support will be enhanced with parameters and options for describing various AD options in a scene. The editing tools will be adapted accordingly to support editing of AD parameters.

4. SIGN LANGUAGE PROGRESS

As explained in 1.1. third task of WP4 (T4.3) focuses on sign language. In the first iteration of ImAc, the objective of T4.3 is defined to be development of technological basis for sign languages and also investigation of SL accessibility content formats:

- Development of an editing tool for SL video assets enrichment with metadata for a 360°/VR environment (see chapter 4.1)
- Easy to user GUI interface
- Ensure compatibility between main video and SL

In this section, the progress in the SL production tools is presented, result and the intended future work.

4.1. WEB SL EDITOR

For this first iteration the Editor interface (see illustration 2) and a Web SL Editor should be developed.

The Editor interface is a place in which the professional users can see and navigate the tasks that have been assigned to them previously from the Content Manager interface. These tasks can be either a ST, AD or SL. In this subsection we deal with SL tasks which are performed by the integrated Web SL Editor.

4.1.1. General description

As no current SL Editor seems to exist we base our development on current ST and AD production tool interfaces. Also support for 360° video and enhanced metadata elements will be implemented. As seen before the user requirements are extracted from D2.2 and the specifications are from D2.3. it is very important for this tool to maintain similarities with the current ST and AD tools for the professional user to accept it in an easy way. In 4.1.2. we will take a look at the objectives that were extracted from D2.2 and D2.3 and then in 4.1.3. we see the justifications on why the results are to be completed based on 4.1.2. Finally in 4.1.4. we explain the work to be done in this area.

4.1.2. Objectives

Similar to 2.2.2. we first present the specifications needed for the tool and then the PUR are presented as objectives of this development as two sub-categories:

1. General goals elaborated in D2.3 document.
2. Specific requirements elaborated in D2.2 with their specifications.

1. General goals elaborated in D2.3 (only related to professional users):

- During the first iteration for the production of the pilot's accessibility contents, the video will be uploaded to the Accessibility Content Manager and the Web SL Editor prototype will select the required video from the Accessibility Content Manager
- In the same way, during the first iteration, Accessibility Content Manager will be used for the management of SL files, but it is foreseen to allow directly loading and saving SL files from the computer hard drive on the second iteration
- A 360° preview player for the low-resolution video playback will be embedded in the editor
- The creation of a new sign language segment with characteristics mentioned in D2.3
- The sign language video segment will be previewed alongside the video for real time checking, so the producer can have an instant simulation of the result. The main video playback will be in the preview player and the sign language video segment playback with the interpreter will be in a separate window next to the player
- The editor will be able to show graphical elements that inform about the orientation of the current speaker, so the professional user can have a simulation of the result
- The professional user will be able to check the final result. In this case the sign language video segment will be played in a window next to the preview player in a synchronized manner
- The final check of the complete result in high quality video can be done using HMD

2. Specific PURs elaborated in D2.2 with their specifications:

Req. Nr.	Title	Description
PUR.01.01.0	Watch low-res preview content	The user must be able to watch the preview content in low quality as flat folded or flat unfolded view.
PUR.01.02.0	Watch hi-res preview content	The user must be able to watch the preview content in high quality as HMD view.
PUR.01.03.0	Navigate preview content by angle	The user must be able to watch content and to navigate it with the help of keyboard shortcuts, scroll wheel and input fields by angle.
PUR.01.04.0	Navigate preview content by frame	The user must be able to watch content and to navigate it with the help of keyboard shortcuts, scroll wheel and input fields by frame number.
PUR.01.05.0	Navigate preview content by time	The user must be able to watch content and to navigate it with the help of keyboard shortcuts, scroll wheel and input fields by time code.
PUR.01.07.0	File operations	The user must be able to perform file operations such as import or export files (video and ImAc files).
PUR.01.09.0	Add sign language video	The user must be able to add sign language video with the following ordered steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Separating specific SL segments if necessary 2. Defining dimensions of SL video 3. Defining vertical and horizontal position 4. Defining time-code 5. Defining viewing angle
PUR.03.01.0	Accessing content for ImAc enrichment	The user should use a GUI for accessing omnidirectional (video) and ImAc content files (ST, SL video, AD) for selecting and uploading/downloading files.
PUR.03.04.0	Triggering content packaging and distribution	The user must be able to trigger and monitor the packaging of open and closed ST, SL and AD enhanced media items.
PUR.03.05.0	Checking state of content packaging and distribution	The user must be able to check the state of packaging of enhanced media items.
PUR.03.06.0	Locally retrieving the packaging result	The user must be able to direct the packaged ImAc result as local retrieval.
PUR.03.07.0	Directing the packaging result to a different resource	The user must be able to direct the packaged ImAc result forwarded to a different resource.
PUR.03.08.0	Configure the signalisation of ImAc services	The user should be able to configure signalisation of ImAc content for distribution and playback.

Table 14: Professional User Requirements in SL Production tool

4.1.3. Results

At the end of first iteration, no result is presented for this task. Due to the decision we made on putting main focus of the project on finishing the development of the CM and Web ST and AD Editors, on the first due date of this deliverable which is M10, the development of the Web SL Editor has not started yet. It is expected to start the process of development in M12.

This decision helps the developed tools to be more accurate and close to the specifications and user requirements and also has given us enough time to test CM and ED interfaces in a timely manner and successfully.

Also the activities in T4.3 is harmonized with the tasks we did in T4.1 and T4.2 and strategies for handling SL and AD is similar, hence having clear and complete results in those tasks help us better to work properly in T4.3.

4.1.4. Future work and second iteration

The future work of this task includes starting to work on the objectives in 4.1.2. based on strategies explained in 4.1.

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